

Canonical Partition Function and Information Theory

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In (1), it is argued that an ensemble of systems may be arranged $W = M! / [m_1! m_2! \dots]$ ways subject to $\sum_i m_i = M$ ((1a)) and $\sum_i m_i E_i = U$ ((1b)). m_i represents the number of systems with energy E_i . (Note: In (1) systems in an ensemble do not interact and each consists of many interacting particles.) The average number of systems with E_i may be calculated from:

$$\langle m_i \rangle = \sum_{\{m_i\}} m_i W(\{m_i\}) / \sum_{\{m_i\}} W(\{m_i\}) \quad ((2))$$

Here $\{m_i\}$ is a set of m_i values satisfying ((1a)) and ((1b)). In (1) arguments using generalizations to the complex plane, saddle points and contour integration are used to argue that $\langle m_i \rangle = M \exp(-E_i/T) / \sum_i \exp(-E_i/T)$ ((3))

This result may also be obtained by maximizing W subject to the constraints ((1a)) and ((1b)), but the objective of the calculation of ((1)) is not to use maximization.

In this note, we wish to argue that the approach of (1) leads to Shannon's entropy and makes use of information theory (as presented in (2)), although these terms are not mentioned in (1). Thus, we wish to show the link between the statistical mechanical canonical partition function and Shannon's entropy. We would also like to point out that if one applies Stirling's approximation to W initially, one may obtain Shannon's entropy without any generalization to the complex plane, saddle point or contour integration. It should be noted, however, that Stirling's approximation is obtained using saddle point integration (so one is not really bypassing such calculations).

It is possible the link between Information theory (Shannon's entropy) and the canonical distribution has been pointed out already in the literature. The review paper (2) of information theory mentions links between physics and information theory, but does not seem to present the calculation of (1). It does, however, mention a link between the canonical partition function and information theory (equation 48 in (2)).

Maximization of Ensemble Arrangements

Given $W = M! / [m_1! m_2! \dots]$ subject to $\sum_i m_i = M$ and $\sum_i m_i E_i = U$, one may ask for the set of m_i which maximize W . This problem may be solved simply if Stirling's approximation:

$$\ln(m!) = m \ln(m) - m \approx m \ln(m) \quad ((3)) \text{ is used.}$$

Then, one finds: $m_i = C \exp(-E_i/T)$ where C is a normalization constant. This is the special equilibrium set of $\{m_i\}$.

In (1), the objective, however, is not to use the maximization, but rather to explicitly calculate $\langle m_i \rangle = \frac{[\text{Sum over } \{m_i\} m_i W(m_i)]}{[\text{Sum over } \{m_i\} W(m_i)]}$ ((4))

Thus, one sums over all possible sets of $\{m_i\}$ such that there is a total of M systems and the energy contained in the sum of all systems is MU . The equilibrium set should be one of many sets. It should be noted that in the calculation of ((4)), only sets with large m_i values dominate. In fact, from the maximization approach, one knows that W for the equilibrium is a maximum, which means W for other sets is smaller. Given these two ideas, it seems one may write W in an approximate form using Stirling's approximation $\ln(m!) = m \ln(m)$. Then:

$\ln(W) = \ln(M!) - \text{Sum over } i m_i \ln(m_i)$ ((5)) The second term on the RHS is Shannon's entropy.

Thus: $\langle m_i \rangle = \frac{\{\text{Sum over } \{m_i\} m_i \text{Exp}[-\text{Sum over } i m_i \ln(m_i)]\}}{\{\text{Sum over } \{m_i\} \text{Exp}[-\text{Sum over } i m_i \ln(m_i)]\}}$

If Shannon's entropy is sharply peaked for a special set of $\{m_i\}$ (i.e. the equilibrium set) then to first order:

$\langle m_i \rangle = m_i$ of the equilibrium set ((6))

Thus, one may maximize Shannon's entropy subject to ((1a)) and ((1b)) to find the special set of $\{m_i\}$ namely $m_i = C \exp(-E_i/T)$. This is basically the same approach used in maximizing W in the first part of the section.

Calculation from (1)

Next, let us briefly outline the full procedure from (1) (used to calculate ((4))) without using Stirling's approximation. It will be seen that Shannon's entropy appears in this approach as well, although it is not directly labelled as such.

(1) begins by defining: $W(m_k) = \frac{M! g_0^{m_0} g_1^{m_1} \dots}{[m_0! m_1! \dots]}$ ((7))

Here g_i is a parameter which is set to 1 at the end of the calculation. It is introduced so $\langle m_k \rangle$ may be defined in terms of a derivative of the \ln of a function namely:

$Q(M,U) = \text{Sum over } \{m_i\} W(\{m_i\})$ ((8)) i.e. $\langle m_i \rangle = g_i \frac{d}{dg_i} \ln(Q)$ ((9))

$Q(M,U)$ is then generalized to: $G(M,z) = \text{Sum } U=0 \text{ to infinite } z^{MU} Q(M,U)$ ((10))

where z is a complex variable.

After some algebra, it is found that $Q(M,U) = 1 / (6.28i) \text{ Contour Integral } [f(z)]^M / z^{MU+1}$ ((11))

where $f(z) = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} g_k z^{E_k}$ ((12))

Next, the integrand of ((11)) is written as $I(z) = \exp[M g(z)]$ where $g(z) = \ln(f) - U \ln(z)$ ((13))

In (1), it is argued that $I(z)$ has a maximum (moving along the i axis) at $z=x_0$ such that:

$d/dz g(z)$ eval at $x_0 = 0$ from which it directly follows that

$[\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} E_k x_0^{E_k}] / [\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_0^{E_k}] = U$ ((13))

At this point, we argue Shannon's entropy is already used. Furthermore, it seems one has a solution as ((13)) yields a probability set $x_0^{E_k} / [\sum_{k=0}^{\infty} x_0^{E_k}]$ which maximizes the integrand. If one writes $x_0 = \exp(-1/T)$, one obtains the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution.

Furthermore, $g(z) = \ln(f) - U \ln(z)$ is directly related to Shannon's entropy as can be seen as follows:

Shannon's entropy = - Integral phase space $\sum_{i=1}^n n(e_i) \ln(n(e_i))$ ((14))

Here $n(e_i) = m_i/M$ i.e. n_i is a probability

But for the MB distribution $\ln(n(e_i)) = \ln(C) - e_i/T$ where C is the normalization constant equivalent. Thus, ((14)) becomes for $z=z_0$:

Shannon's entropy = $U \ln(z_0) - \ln(f)$

which is exactly the definition used in (1). Thus, the integrand $I(z)$ is $\exp(\text{Shannon's entropy})$. This seems to be identical to the result from section 1 in which $\ln(m_i!)$ is replaced with $m_i \ln(m_i)$ and one finds the maximum value of Shannon's entropy subject to energy and count constraints.

An interesting point of (1), however, is that Shannon's entropy may be expanded about the maximum to yield fluctuations. The integrand is $I(z) = \exp(Mg(z))$ and $g(x_0)$ is a maximum, thus:

$g(z) = g(x_0) + .5(z-x_0)^2 d^2/dz^2 g(x_0)$ ((15))

This is then integrated to yield a fluctuation factor i.e.

$G(M,U) = \exp(Mg(x_0)) / (6.28) \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dy \exp[-.5 M d^2/dz^2 g(x_0) y^2]$ which may be solved in closed form. The fluctuations are said in (1) to disappear as M goes to infinite, but might be useful for systems with finite M .

Thus, the calculation in (1) using saddle points, generalizations to the complex plane and contour integration seems to be directly related to Shannon's entropy. In addition, one may obtain the result, it seems by immediately applying Stirling's approximation to ((4)).

Conclusion

In conclusion, we have tried to argue one may calculate ((4)) i.e. the average number of systems with energy m_i in an ensemble from $M! / [m_1! M_2! \dots]$ by replacing each $\ln(m_i!)$ with $m_i \ln(m_i)$ from Stirling's approximation. The result is $\exp(\text{Shannon's entropy})$, thus maximization of Shannon's entropy subject to an energy and count constraint may yield the result if the integrand is sharply peaked. A more general approach using the generalization of ((4)) to the complex plane, saddle points and contour integration yields a very similar result which also makes use of Shannon's entropy and its maximization. In (1), these calculations are used to establish the canonical partition function approach, thus this approach seems to be directly related to Shannon's entropy and information theory. We have argued in other notes, however, that one may find Maxwell-Boltzmann, Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein distributions by considering time reversal balanced two body collision reactions which does not require any counting or entropy.

References

1. Huang, Kerson. Statistical Mechanics (Wiley, 1987) pages 193 -199
2. Rioul, Oliver. This is IT: A Primer on Shannon's Entropy and Information 2018

<http://www.bourbaphy.fr/rioul.pdf>